

Toward an In Vitro Preparation to Study the Cochlear Active Process of Mammals

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Abstract. The mammalian cochlea is powered by an active process characterized by amplification of mechanical inputs, sharp frequency selectivity, compressive nonlinearity, and spontaneous otoacoustic emission. Similar traits are observed in individual hair cells of nonmammalian tetrapods, in which they emerge from the critical dynamical regime of hair cells operating near a Hopf bifurcation. It remains unclear whether criticality also underpins the active process of the mammalian cochlea. To probe this question, we conducted electrophysiological recordings of microphonic signals in isolated cochlear segments of the Mongolian gerbil. We did so by improving the two-compartment cochlear preparation originally developed by Chan and Hudspeth to more closely simulate *in vivo* conditions. Our methodological advances included refining the dissection protocol to reduce the size of the exposed cochlear segment and altering the ionic compositions of the solutions to better control the Ca^{2+} concentration. We also maintained a constant temperature in order to stabilize the experimental conditions. Most critically, by introducing a mechanism to adjust the pressure in the endolymphatic compartment, we were able to explore how variations in pressure influence the electrical response. These changes enabled us to reliably measure compressive nonlinearities with a one-third power law similar to that observed in intact cochleae *in vivo*.

INTRODUCTION

At the core of hearing there is an active process that the ear employs to amplify sounds. Although disruption of this process causes hearing loss, the mechanism by which it operates remains unclear. The active process optimizes the ear's response to sound through three defining characteristics: it expends energy to amplify stimuli, sharpens acoustic responses through frequency specificity, and demonstrates compressive nonlinearity. The system condenses a broad intensity range of input signals into a narrower output range and thereby increases the ear's sensitivity to softer sounds while preventing damage from louder ones.

The active process is thought to originate from the activity of hair cells, the sensory receptors of the ear. These cells act as microphones, for they pick up sound vibrations with their mechanosensitive structures, as well as amplifiers that enhance the stimuli that they receive. Their operation relies on molecular springs, the tip links, that connect to mechanically sensitive ion channels that open and close them in unison with periodic stimuli. These cells are located in the organ of Corti, an intricate sensory epithelium situated between the tectorial and basilar membranes and stretching along the entire cochlear spiral. The somata of the hair cells, which are interspersed among supporting cells in the organ of Corti, are positioned atop the basilar membrane and in contact with an extracellular fluid called *perilymph*. The cells' sensory microvilli—grouped into hair bundles—extend into a chamber filled with a Na^{2+} -poor solution called *endolymph*, with the gel-like tectorial membrane resting upon them [3].

When sound-driven vibrations reach the cochlea, they generate a traveling wave that progresses along the basilar membrane from the cochlea's base toward its apex. This wave peaks at a specific location along the cochlear spiral that depends on the frequency of the sound. High frequencies provoke the greatest movement in the basal portion of the organ of Corti, whereas lower frequencies propagate further along the spiral to activate more apical areas. The high sensitivity of hearing results from the synergy between the traveling wave and active movements within the organ

of Corti, as sustained by the hair cells.

Two principal theories have been proposed to account for the active process in mammals: membrane-based somatic electromotility and active hair-bundle motility [2, 4]. The first involves a strictly mammalian type of hair cell, the outer hair cell, which is capable of changing its length in response to changes in the membrane potential. The latter process, which has been demonstrated in non-mammalian vertebrates, involves the hair bundle's capacity to exert forces that amplify mechanical stimuli. Together with a Ca^{2+} -dependent adaptation mechanism, myosin motors located at the upper end of the tip links situate the system near a dynamical instability known as the Hopf bifurcation [4, 6].

The exact mechanism by which individual hair cells contribute to the overall active process observed in the cochlea remains elusive. This problem stems in part from the challenging nature of studying hair cells *in vitro*. Encased within the dense temporal bone, the cochlea poses a formidable barrier to direct examination, and dissection typically leads to significant structural changes as well as cellular intoxication owing to the mixing of endolymph and perilymph.

In 2005, Chan and Hudspeth pioneered the creation of a two-compartment experimental preparation that preserved the essential features of the cochlea [1]. However, they were unable to observe nonlinearities whose slopes closely matched those that characterize the active process in healthy cochleae. Building upon their work, we revisited and refined their protocol by implementing several critical improvements. By this means we were able to reliably measure in excised cochlear segments compressive nonlinearities comparable to those observed in intact cochleae.

FIGURE 1: Tuning and compressive nonlinearity in an isolated cochlear segment. (A) In the normalized microphonic response as a function of frequency for a 200 ms frequency-sweep stimulus of 500-3000 Hz, the peak near 1000 Hz is suggestive of a resonance within the experimental apparatus. The peaks observed at higher frequencies bracket a plateau that defines the characteristic frequencies of the sensory hair cells under investigation. (B) A level function portrays the response of the same cochlear segment to a single tone at 2660 Hz with the artificial endocochlear potential set at 100 mV (black circles). The amplitude of the cochlear microphonic voltage increases sublinearly for low stimulus pressures, transitioning to a linear increase at higher levels. In the absence of an endocochlear potential (empty circles), the overall microphonic response diminishes and the signal emerges from the noise floor (black dotted line) in a linear fashion. In these doubly logarithmic plots, two dashed gray lines have been included for reference, one representing linear growth and the other a slope of 1/3. (C) When the same data are plotted on terms of sensitivity the lines instead represent a null and a $-2/3$ slope.

METHODS

All procedures involving animals were conducted following the guidelines approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee of Rockefeller University. Mongolian gerbils of three to four weeks' age and both sexes were euthanized by intraperitoneal injection of 200 mg·kg⁻¹ pentobarbital sodium and phenytoin sodium (Euthasol®). The cochleae were excised and placed in a petri dish with dissecting solution containing 155 mM Na⁺, 3 mM K⁺, 250 μM Ca²⁺, 1 mM Mg²⁺, 154 mM Cl⁻, 1 mM HPO²⁻, 5 mM HEPES, 3 mM pyruvate, and 10 mM D(+)-glucose and with a pH of 7.3-7.4 and an osmolarity of 310 mOsm·kg⁻¹ [1]. We next transected the cochlea perpendicular to its helical axis, specifically between the basal and middle turns, and secured the isolated middle turn across a 1.5 mm hole in a plastic disk with isobutyl 2-cyanoacrylate₄ (BOC Sciences). We then created optical access by opening windows in the thin bone layers that form the ceiling and floor of the middle cochlear turn and directly exposed the sensory epithelium of that turn. We sealed all openings to the cochlear duct with cyanoacrylate adhesive to prevent any leakage along the cochlear spiral. We removed Reissner's membrane and oriented the disk in a two-compartment recording chamber. This entire procedure was generally accomplished within about 20 minutes. The basal surface of the cochlear segment was immersed in an artificial perilymph that included the above dissecting solution enhanced with a Ca^{2+} concentration adjusted to 2 mM. The apical surface was exposed to an artificial endolymph that contained 150 mM KCl, 25 μM CaCl₂, 1 mM sodium pyruvate, 5 mM D-glucose, and 10 mM HPO²⁻ at a pH of 7.35. We

maintained all experimental solutions in an oxygenated state and utilized them at a consistent room temperature of 20-24 °C.

Acoustic stimuli were delivered to the lower compartment through high-performance speakers (Etymotic Research; ER-3C). The sound pressure was calibrated with a free-field microphone (4939-A-011, Bruel & Kjaer). A pair of Ag/AgCl electrodes provided a steady endocochlear potential of 90-100 mV between the endolymphatic compartment and the perilymphatic one. A second pair of Ag/AgCl electrodes placed in the vicinity of the cochlear partition acquired cochlear-microphonic potentials in response to stimulation. In each experiment the noise floor from the microphonic signal was estimated as three times the standard deviation of the microphonic potential's amplitude at five consecutive frequency bins 1000 Hz distant from the stimulus frequency.

FIGURE 2: Examples of level functions and the corresponding sensitivity plots in three different cochlear segments. (A-C) The nonlinear range of responsiveness spans one to two orders of magnitude in sound pressure. In each instance the perilymphatic compartment—the basolateral epithelial surface—faced upward. As in Fig. 1B, the black dotted lines delineate the noise floor and the pairs of grey dashed lines represent linear and nonlinear growths.

RESULTS

Compressive nonlinearity in excised cochlear segments

At the beginning of each experiment, the range of characteristic frequencies represented in an excised cochlear segment was determined by delivering a calibrated chirp, or frequency sweep, covering 500-4000 Hz and recording the cochlear microphonic (CM) response. The resulting signals typically displayed a low-frequency peak centered near 1 kHz—possibly the result of a resonance in the apparatus—and a plateau between 2 kHz and 3 kHz (Fig. 1A). This range of frequencies coincides with the range of characteristic frequencies expected from the location of the exposed segment of sensory tissue along the tonotopic axis of the cochlear spiral [5]. When stimulated at a frequency within this range of characteristic frequencies, the same cochlear segment displayed compressive nonlinearity similar to that observed in an intact, healthy cochlea [9, 8].

Fig. 1B portrays the microphonics responses to single-tone sound stimuli at a frequency $f_{stim} = 2.66$ kHz as a function of sound-pressure levels. This cochlear segment showed characteristic frequencies ranging from 2 Hz to 3 kHz. At low sound-pressure levels, the magnitude of the response currents increased sublinearly with a slope of approximately 1/3. As the sound-pressure levels rose, this growth transitioned to a linear regime.

The transition was more obvious in plots of the segment's sensitivity, defined as the amplitude of the microphonic response at f_{stim} relative to the pressure at that level (Fig. 1C). In this case, the nonlinear response decreased with a slope of approximately -2/3 with increasing sound pressure levels, then settled on a null slope after the response of the segment had become proportional to the intensity of the stimulus. This nonlinearity was contingent upon the

presence of an imposed endocochlear potential. In Fig. 2 we showcase other examples of compressive nonlinearities with a 1/3 power-law slope, as measured from different cochlear segments.

Effect of pressure differences across the cochlear partition

We observed that cochlear segments, when positioned with the perilymph compartment facing upward and the hair bundles pointed downward toward the sound source, exhibited more consistent compressive nonlinearities. We speculated that this effect resulted from the biasing of the tissue imparted by the mass of saline solution weighing upon the cochlear partition.

To test this hypothesis, we modified the apparatus to impose static pressures in the lower compartment to counteract the load over the cochlear partition. Because the stimulus speakers were internally vented to atmospheric pressure, we wrapped their casings with Parafilm™ to prevent pressure leakage. We then connected to the chamber's lower compartment a U-tube system partially filled with water. By adding or subtracting controlled amounts of water at the opposite, open end, we imposed controlled static pressures.

While recording the cochlear microphonic responses with a frequency sweep of 300-3000 Hz, we progressively increased the pressure in the lower compartment. In the absence of any imposed pressure difference the preparation did not exhibit frequency tuning (Fig. 3A). As we gradually increased the pressure in the lower compartment, the cochlear microphonic responses began to display two distinct peaks, the magnitude of which varied depending on the pressure difference.

In another experiment in which we exposed a segment centered near the apical end of the second turn, we applied a series of sweeps at different sound-pressure levels. At each pressure level, we mapped the level function at the peak frequency (Fig. 3B). We observed that there was an optimal pressure at which the microphonic responses showed clear compression.

FIGURE 3: The effect of static pressure on the microphonic response. (A) In the absence of a pressure difference across the cochlear partition (continuous line)—here mounted with the endolymphatic surface uppermost—the response to a frequency sweep of 300-3000 Hz displayed no peaks. However, as the pressure in the lower compartment increased (dotted and dashed lines), peaks emerged at approximately 600 Hz and 1100 Hz. (B) In a different experiment, the preparation was mounted with the perilymphatic compartment uppermost. Plots of level functions at a peak frequency of 600 Hz reveal the effects of larger positive and negative pressure biases in the lower compartment. (C) The corresponding sensitivity curves reveal a slope of -2/3 at low levels of stimulation and a slope of zero (linear responsiveness) at high levels.

DISCUSSION

By refining the methodology developed earlier [1], we enhanced the two-compartment cochlear preparation to more establish *in vitro* the conditions necessary to measure compressive nonlinearities that closely resembled those observed in intact cochleae. In particular, we optimized the dissection protocol, improved the chemical composition of the physiological solutions, and maintained the excised sensory tissue at a constant temperature.

We additionally determined the importance of the pressure difference across the cochlear segment for the emergence of a compressive nonlinearity. As the pressure difference changed, it is highly likely that the resting position of the cochlear partition was also altered. This in turn influenced the resting state of the mechanosensitive ion channels, whose opening and closing underlie all models of the cochlear active process.

A 10 mm column of solution in the upper compartment is expected to exert a hydrostatic pressure of about 99 Pa on the sensory tissue. Given an opening area $A = 500 \text{ mm} \times 70 \text{ mm} = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2$, this pressure translates into a total force of 3.46 mN. Considering a point stiffness of the sensory tissue of $120 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ [1, 7], we can estimate that the

hydrostatic pressure displaces the tissue by approximately 30 nm, enough to significantly affect the resting position of the mechanosensitive ion channels. Because this estimate does not take into account the variability in size of the cochlear partition and the effect that might have on the areal stiffness, it is challenging to determine the tissue's physiological resting position.

Given this complexity, developing an experimental system that minimizes or eliminates these biases would be highly beneficial. A vertical chamber, for example, could reduce gravitational effects that might alter the natural resting position of cochlear components and thus foster a more accurate representation of *in vivo* conditions. Such an approach could lead to more precise measurements and a deeper understanding of cochlear operation under physiological conditions.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Bastian Epp: Dear Francesco (et al)! Thanks for the manuscript draft - it was an exciting read (and exciting to see the work at MOH). The experiment is impressive and the work definitely targets some highly relevant questions that will help to merge the two worlds of mammals and amphibians and will (hopefully) help the community to resolve some of the open issues. I provide my comments in order along the manuscript to make it easier for you to revise. Please get back if you need more details/explanations. **GENERAL:** The manuscript is over page limit. I see how you are developing a full-sized paper, but for the proceedings, this is too long. I provide some comments below on how to condense the manuscript. Besides those, I would argue, that one might put the focus even more on the experimental technique. The manuscript suggests that there might be many more answers than it in the end provides. The biggest values in the paper are the refinements and the **POTENTIAL** to get insights into mammalian cochlear processing. But the data are still a bit unclear and depend on too many uncertainties regarding the chemical composition, the orientation, the "right" pressure, etc. so cutting the more general frame and focusing on the experiments as a POC will sharpen the argument (and I am sure even more people will appreciate it!).

Francesco Gianoli: Thank you for your positive feedback regarding the manuscript. We appreciate your recognition of the experiment's significance and its potential to bridge the gap between mammalian and amphibian research. We have reviewed your comments, and we shall address them in detail below.

Bastian Epp: One point to consider is (e.g. in the **ABSTRACT**) that an important difference between your measurements (electrical) vs some of the classical work is, that you measure essentially "gross" responses - meaning that you can't really be sure to look at one point/cell. You don't have a bead or a laser pointed at some specific spatial location. But this is an advantage: non-invasive electrophysiology does the same in humans - and so does psychophysics! But this makes it hard to link 1:1 to hair bundle dynamics. A careful statement on this in the **DISCUSSION** might be helpful.

Francesco Gianoli: As you point out, we are not recording from one hair cell. At the same time our cochlear microphonics are not measuring a cochlea-wide response as in non-invasive electrophysiology or in psychophysics. Our cochlear segments are roughly 500 μm long and can hence be estimated to comprise 50 columns of four hair cells 10 μm apart, or roughly 200 hair cells. The other portions of the tonotopic axis that fall outside the exposed cochlear segment cannot contribute to the cochlear microphonics because they are either fixed in adhesive or completely absent from the preparation.

Bastian Epp: **INTRO:** "Their working relies on..." -> You can cut this w/o losing information. - and even shorten more of the remaining paragraph down to "...resting upon them...". This might help to shorten the **INTRODUCTION** in general. Many of the points are relevant and important - but given that you don't look for a travelling wave but mainly want to see basic characteristics due to the refined experiment, some of those details can be cut at this point.

Francesco Gianoli: We shortened the text in the Introduction as suggested.

Bastian Epp: "However, the exact mechanisms..": I'd argue that it might be great to help the readers to recall the amphibian hair cells do not have prestin. This does not exclude the possibility of HB motility contribution in mammals, but it might accommodate the arguments **AGAINST** the 1:1 comparison of amphibians with mammals.

Francesco Gianoli: We agree that it would be important to emphasize the difference between amphibian and mammalian hair cells. Indeed, the active process manifests similar features in both amphibians and mammals, despite the complete absence of prestin and electromotility in amphibians. This observation is significant, for it suggests that hair bundle motility is potentially capable of sustaining the cochlear active process by itself. We cannot conclude that idea from our work, nor we claim to do so.

Bastian Epp: "By adjusting the pressure..": This might be a critical point - you don't really know that the "ideal" pressure balance is. all you can state is, that it affects the dynamic behavior - I would be reluctant to follow your argument that it is more "optimal" function in-vivo.

Francesco Gianoli: We agree that we do not know the static pressure, if any, across the sensory epithelium of an intact cochlea. In our experiments we merely wish to avoid an artificial bias on the resting position of the cochlear partition due to the weight of the solution above it. We believe that it will be valuable for experimentalists to be aware

of this potential problem. We are working on a new apparatus that would allow us to avoid such gravitational bias altogether without the need for compensation with pressure in the lower compartment.

Bastian Epp: The acoustic stimulation, in your preparation, is delivered through the lower chamber. It might be good to discuss how realistic that is. The energy is not coming from the middle ear. I see the necessity (the experiment is already complex). But this is important when interpreting the data.

Francesco Gianoli: Our system is intentionally reduced for the sake of simplicity and to allow for more direct manipulations and measurement of cochlear processes. In that sense it is as realistic as other experimental models such as electrophysiological recordings in tissue culture. It is important to point out that the stimulation is highly analogous to bone conduction, which is a relevant topic in the field.

Bastian Epp: I have a hard time understanding the multiple peaks. Resonance in the chamber might be one explanation (does the geometry match?). The data also look suspiciously like harmonic distortion. Did you look at the sound source at the use driving pressure?

Francesco Gianoli: The dimensions of the chamber are unlikely to elicit a resonance at those frequencies, but we cannot exclude them. Nevertheless, after using chirps to assess the tuning of the cochlear segment, we performed single-tone stimulation to assess the nonlinear level functions. We focused our attention on the higher-frequency peaks that revealed nonlinear responses and whose frequencies fell within the range of frequencies expected from the tonotopic placement of the exposed cochlear segment. We never observed nonlinear responses when stimulating at the lower-frequency peak. Indeed, the lower-frequency peaks are unchanged across preparations, unlike the higher-frequency peaks that depend on the tonotopic position.

Bastian Epp: The Figures have in general too small labels and are hard to read. You might consider combining FIG 1+2 to save space. Are FIG 1 and 2 the same preparation?

Francesco Gianoli: We increased the labels. No, Figure 2 includes three different examples from three preparations, none of which is shown in Figure 1

Bastian Epp: "...seems to be an optimal pressure..." -> Same point as above. optimal for what you want to see. Not necessarily optimal for the operation in-vivo.

Francesco Gianoli: We made this clear in the text.

Bastian Epp: DISCUSSION: "...opening and closing underlie all.." -> Not necessary to mention. It is correct, but might be misleading when comparing mammals and amphibians (IHC/OHC). And it will save you space.

Francesco Gianoli: We changed "This in turn influenced the resting state of the mechanosensitive ion channels, whose opening and closing underlie all models of the cochlear active process." to "This in turn influenced the resting state of the mechanosensitive ion channels, whose opening and closing underlie cochlear active processes."

Bastian Epp: Fig 3: Again, too small for the requested format. And panel A looks suspiciously like harmonic distortion - can you rule out distortion in the sound source? I am looking forward to seeing this work in condensed form in the proceedings. A great step into important experiments to come! Greetings! Bastian.

Francesco Gianoli: We calibrated the speaker and we did not observe any distortions in the sound source. Notice that chirp stimuli have been used only to identify the tuning of the cochlear segment. The nonlinear responses were measured in response to single tones. The microphone recordings of the stimuli were calibrated and showed no distortions.

The following questions refer to the talk, which included Optical Coherence Vibrometry data:

Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh: It appeared that there was some nonlinearity away from the characteristic frequency, and it also seemed that the response was nonlinear in some regions but linear in others within the Organ of Corti, even within the same preparation.

Francesco Gianoli: Yes, that is the case. The intensity of the vibration grows linearly in response to growing intensity of sound stimuli in some parts of the Organ of Corti and linearly in others.

Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh: What about the nonlinearity away from the characteristic frequency. What is the nonlinear slope away from the CF?

Francesco Gianoli: Away from characteristic frequency the slope becomes progressively more linear. I did not quantify it next to the figure I have shown, but it becomes fully linear if the stimulus frequency is far enough from the characteristic frequency.

Cristopher Bergevin: Given that this is a nonlinear dynamics session, I have a basic question: in a dynamical system close to a Hopf bifurcation the response grows as the cubic root of the driving force. Yet, in a lot of data you see a one-third power law in the compression regime, but you also see linearity at the lower intensity levels. What is the rationale?

Francesco Gianoli: There is a difference between Hopf in its simplest mathematical form and a Hopf system in the real world and that has something to do with the presence of noise. At low intensity levels you do expect to observe a linear slope in a system near Hopf. You see it in individual hair bundles in the bullfrog, whose behavior have been shown to be that of a system poised near a Hopf bifurcation. At low intensities of the stimulus force the response grows linearly first, then it becomes nonlinear with a one-third power law and then linear again at higher levels. In mathematical terms, we can show this by adding an extra noise term to the normal form. At lower intensity levels, the extra noise term effectively de-tunes the system, which makes the response grow linearly as a function of the driving force.

Julien Meaud: My question is related because I think the way you describe the *in vivo* data does not match with what I think about it. I think that if you look at *in vivo* data, at the characteristic frequency, at low levels, you see a linear growth. You don't see this nonlinear growth you are talking about.

Francesco Gianoli: Yes, you see the same in an individual hair bundle in the bullfrog. The linear slope at low intensities levels is well within expectations from a dynamical system near a Hopf bifurcation in a biological setting. I have chosen *in vivo* data from Ruggero, which do not show a linear growth at low levels, to introduce the concept of one-third slopes. In our cochlear segments we rarely observe these linear regimes at low intensities, perhaps because of the stimulus delivery system that cannot reach those very low intensity levels, but we do see reliable one-third nonlinear slopes.